

ACCESSIBILITY, PERCEIVED EASE OF USE AND READINESS TO ADOPT ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN SCHOOLS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence has the potential to present numerous advantages to educators and to bring about sustainable development, they can help educators plan and prepare engaging lessons to promote better learning outcomes, empowering them for sustainability and improved collaboration. This paper explores Educators' Accessibility, Perceived Ease of Use and Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence for Instructional Delivery in Schools FOR sustainable development in Kwara state. The study adopted descriptive research method of the survey type. Three research questions were answered, and two research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population for the study was all educators in both public and private institutions of learning in Kwara state. Samples were drawn randomly, respondents from three secondary schools, three college of education, and three universities. A researcher designed well-structured questionnaire used to elicit information from the 53 respondents. The 35 items questionnaire of 4 points Likert scale was titled "Educators' Accessibility, Perceived Ease of Use and Readiness to Adopt of Artificial Intelligence for Instructional Practices Questionnaire (EAPEUARAIO)" findings revealed that Educators' level of accessibility to artificial intelligence varies and does not significantly influence their readiness to adopt it. This paper recommends that one way of overcoming the challenges of accessibility is to train school teachers, enlighten educators and empower them with artificial intelligence tools that can be easily accessed to achieve sustainable development in the country.

Keywords: Educators, Professional Development, Artificial Intelligence, Perceived Ease of Use, Instructional Delivery, Readiness to Adopt.

Introduction

The use of computers in education has a history spanning many decades, with relatively varied effects. Computers have not always helped produce the benefits their proponents envisioned (McFarlane, 2019). Hence, Sadiku et al. (2021) describe the notion of artificial intelligence (AI)

as the capacity of a computer system to accomplish human activities (such as thinking and learning) that can normally only be performed by human intelligence. AI technology in education gives a degree of flexibility and customisation that has never been feasible before. This is transforming schools and classrooms, making a teacher's work much simpler. AI is set to transform schooling. John McCarthy proposed the name Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the 1950s, characterising it as "the science and engineering of making intelligent machines." Since then, the discipline has developed and so has the concept of AI.

Currently, a single general definition of AI does not exist. This is mainly owing to the fast progress of discipline, but also because scholars outside of computer science in the fields of education, philosophy, economics, and the arts have developed a tremendous interest in AI and its application. Each of these study disciplines has changed the word AI to reflect its own requirements and applications, and this multidisciplinary character of AI makes it difficult to reach an agreement about what AI is. In this study, an informal and wide definition of AI was suggested by Popenici and Kerr (2017), who described AI as "computing systems that are able to engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correcting, and using data for complex processing tasks." The article evaluates the accessibility, perceived ease of use, and readiness to adopt AI for instructional delivery in schools. Artificial intelligence (AI) has been widely adopted worldwide as a technology that has the potential to simplify our lives and drive economic growth (European Commission, 2020).

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence for Instruction Delivery to achieve Sustainable Development

AI is been extensively used in several sectors of social systems, it is not exclusive to education. Artificial intelligence (AI) has become a powerful and influential factor in several industries, including the field of education. The reports from UNESCO (Miao et al., 2021) and OECD (2021) present evidence of how AI has enhanced instructional delivery by automating different teaching tasks (such as lesson plan, assessment, and evaluation) through intelligent tutoring systems, and offering new accessible tools (like virtual reality and augmented reality). Researchers have investigated the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in several aspects of education. It is critical to emphasize the huge potential afforded by AI for application in education via the Internet, as well as the accompanying massive improvements that have enabled students and instructors to easily access the knowledge they need and desire to get, this is probably going to lead to the sustainable development needed. As a result, it is critical to take advantage of AI applications and apply them in curriculum creation, teaching techniques, and evaluation to acquire effective learning (Eltabakh, 2019).

Educators anticipate that AI-driven solutions will transform instructional delivery by customising learning experiences, offering immediate feedback, and addressing the unique requirements of students. Nevertheless, accessibility is an essential element that is often overlooked throughout this enthusiasm. Despite the great potential offered by AI-supported learning, AI's extensive use for instructional delivery in schools may not guarantee teachers' ability to employ it in the classroom, and neither does it guarantee the quality of teaching because teachers may not yet be fully prepared to implement AI-based teaching (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, 2019). Moreover, the successful acceptance of new educational practices is intimately tied to the attitudes of instructors towards them. There are still a number of instructors who regard the use of technology in the classroom unfavorably and do not prefer to utilize it but

rather continue to employ conventional teaching materials and approaches. Concern over the adoption of new approaches may limit instructors' attempts to utilize technology in their work (Hébert et al., 2021; Tallvid, 2016).

In this respect, in October 2017, the United Arab Emirates (UAE) became one of the first governments to create a complete strategy for AI, which focused on improving education via AI programs and technologies as one of its primary axes (Sebaa et al., 2018). From this position, the UAE Ministry of Education has endeavored to leverage AI and digital transformation to improve the learning environment in schools. Moreover, the ministry has built and deployed several digital educational platforms in many study disciplines that would help with the integration of education and the development of autonomous self-learning (Minister of State for Artificial Intelligence, 2020). UAE was able to achieve sustainable development through AI.

Accessibility Challenges in the use of AI for Instruction

Despite the promising uses, some accessibility obstacles limit achieving the full potential of AI for inclusive education. Accessibility to digital tools may pose challenges to technology integration and the use of AI for instruction into education. Okada (2018) identified accessibility as one of the major challenges that hindered the wide use of new technologies in education. In many developed countries, this is not a problem, there is easy access to computers for students, their teachers and the school administrators, unlike developing countries (LeCun, 2022). Unequal access to technology and dependable internet connections may create a digital gap where teachers from poorer socioeconomic backgrounds or distant places lack the means to benefit from AI-powered technologies. This exacerbates existing educational inequities and needs initiatives to bridge the digital divide and promote fair access for all students. AI-powered websites may have complicated interfaces or lack functionality catering to varied user demands. This may pose issues, impeding their ability to access the platform and connect with instructional materials efficiently. User-centered design concepts that stress accessibility and cater to a broad variety of abilities are vital (Okada, 2018).

Perceived Ease of Use and Readiness to Adopt AI in Schools

The perceived ease of use and readiness for AI in schools is apparently the promise of artificial intelligence (AI) to improve education. However, for this shift to occur, educators and institutions must be ready to adopt AI for instructional delivery. This readiness rests on two major factors: perceived ease of use and perceived utility. The study reviews the available academic research on these aspects and their effect on the adoption of AI in schools. AI adoption provides the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), created by Fred Davis in 1986, which offers a good framework for understanding technology uptake. The TAM states that perceived ease of use (PEU) and perceived usefulness (PU) are the key factors in a user's inclination to embrace a new technology. In the context of AI in education, PEU refers to the educators' impression of how simple it is to understand and utilise AI technologies for training. PU demonstrates their belief in the benefits of AI for improving student learning and classroom efficiency. According to research, there is a strong association between PEU and PU in promoting technology adoption in education. Studies by Chocarro et al. (2021) and Ukoh & Nicholas (2022) emphasised that teachers who find AI technologies user-friendly are more likely to consider them beneficial for teaching. Conversely, complicated or badly designed AI interfaces might induce fear and inhibit instructors' readiness to incorporate them into their classes.

Hwang et al. (2021) studies underline intuitive interface design as the need for user-friendly contacts with AI applications. These interconnection that are clearing, well-organised, and require minimum technical experience are more likely to be seen as straightforward to use by teachers with varied technology backgrounds. Buabeng-Andoh's (2012) research emphasises the importance of adequate training and technical assistance for educators to feel comfortable utilizing AI technologies. Providing educational tools and ongoing support may significantly improve PEU. Strategies for bridging the gap to fostering adoption based on PEU and PU research encourages the following measures to support the use of AI in schools and focus on user-centered design in developing AI solutions with teachers in mind is vital. Involving teachers in the design phase may ensure interfaces are intuitive and processes are optimised for classroom usage. This may help overcome early fears and establish confidence in adopting AI for teaching. Addressing these issues may develop trust and inspire teachers to be more receptive to implementing the accessibility, perceived ease of use and readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery in schools.

Strategies for bridging the gap to fostering adoption based on PEU and PU research encourages the following measures to support the use of AI in schools and focus on user-centered design in developing AI solutions with educators in mind is vital. Involving teachers in the design phase may ensure interfaces are intuitive and processes are optimised for classroom usage. Providing investment in thorough training and continuous assistance for teachers can successfully deploy AI technologies. This may help overcome early fears and establish confidence in adopting AI for teaching. Also, teachers need to see the highlight of AI's benefits as the actual advantage for their pupils and themselves, showcasing success stories and illustrating how AI may improve learning outcomes helps to build a positive image of its usefulness and the address of ethical concerns issues relating to data protection and dependence on AI systems necessitate honest communication. Addressing these issues may develop trust and inspire teachers to be more receptive to implementing the accessibility, perceived ease of use and readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery in schools. This paper examines the readiness to adopt artificial intelligence (AI), in perceived simplicity of use in advancing instructional delivery in schools while also noting the accessibility obstacles that must be resolved.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to find out accessibility, perceived ease of use and readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery by educators in Ilorin, kwara state for sustainable development. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. find out the educators' level of accessibility to artificial intelligence tools.
2. find out the educators' perceived ease of use of artificial intelligence.
3. investigate readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery

Research Questions

The following questions were raised and answered;

1. What level of accessibility do educators have to artificial intelligence tools in Ilorin, Kwara state?
2. What is the perception of educators on the ease of use of artificial intelligence in Ilorin, Kwara state?
3. What is the level of readiness of educators to adopt artificial intelligence in Ilorin, Kwara state?

Research Hypotheses

H0₁: Accessibility does not significantly influence educators' readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery in Ilorin, Kwara State.

H0₂: Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence does not significantly influence biology educators' perceived ease of use of artificial intelligence in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Methodology

This study is descriptive research of the survey type. It investigated educators' accessibility, perceived ease of use and readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery in schools in Ilorin, Kwara state, for sustainable development in Nigeria. The population for the study included educators in both public and private institutions in Ilorin Kwara State Nigeria. Samples were drawn randomly after the institutions had been stratified, respondents were drawn from one federal university, one state university, one private university, one federal college of education, one state college of education, one private college of education, one federal secondary school, one state owned secondary school and one private secondary school. This gives a total of 54 respondents but a respondent withdrew. A researcher designed questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. The 35 items questionnaire of 4 points Likert scale was titled "Educators' accessibility, perceived ease of use and readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery questionnaire (EAPEUARAAIQ)" and it has three sections, section A, B, and C. Section A deals with Educators' biography; it contains information on the respondents' school type, gender, years of experience and information on their professional development. Section B contains a list of Artificial intelligence to check the level of accessibility of educators. Section C contains a list of artificial intelligence to check the perceived ease of use and educators' readiness to adopt AI.

To ensure face and content validity of the instruments, educators' accessibility, perceived ease of use and readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery questionnaire (EAPEUARAAIQ) was given to two experts in Educational Technology Department and two experts in Information and Communication Technology, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin to check whether the instrument will measure what it supposed to measure. Institutions and Educators participating in this research were not exposed to any of risk as it was made known to them that their responses will be treated confidentially and their identities will not be revealed to anyone. Informed consent form was attached to the google forms for educators to indicate their willingness for voluntary participation in the study. The researcher made it clear to the participating educators that their effort, contributions will be treated confidentially and for the purpose of this study only. The data obtained was analyzed and interpreted using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Percentages was used to analyze the personal information provided by the respondents. Mean scores was used to answer the research questions, Pearson moment correlation co-efficient was used to test the hypotheses.

Results

Research One: What level of accessibility do educators have to artificial intelligence tools in Ilorin, Kwara state?

Table 1: Accessibility to Artificial Intelligence

		Accessibility to Artificial Intelligence							
ITEMS		Not Accessible		Partially Accessible		Accessible		Very Accessible	
		Frequ ency	%	Frequ ency	%	Frequ ency	%	Frequ ency	%
1	ChatGPT (Open.ai)	4	7.5	2	3.8	13	24.5	34	64.2
2	Diffit.ai	25	47.2	11	20.8	12	22.6	5	9.4
3	Magic School.ai	26	49.1	9	17.0	10	18.9	8	15.1
4	Bing.ai	14	26.4	6	11.3	14	26.4	19	35.8
5	Presenta tion.ai	14	26.4	4	7.5	18	34.0	17	32.1
6	Schemel y.app	24	45.3	10	18.9	6	11.3	13	24.5
7	Brisk teaching	27	50.9	8	15.1	9	17.0	9	17.0
8	Almanac k.ai	33	62.3	10	18.9	5	9.4	5	9.4
9	Lingotea ch.ai	25	47.2	10	18.9	11	20.8	7	13.2
10	Zozo solutions	29	54.7	11	20.8	6	11.3	7	13.2
11	Bard/Ge mini.ai	23	43.4	10	18.9	10	18.9	10	18.9
TOTAL		244		91		114		134	

Table 1 displays the degree of accessibility of educators to different Artificial Intelligence programs or websites. The data reveals that the category of "not aware" received 244 responses, accounting for 42% of the total. The category of "very aware" received 134 responses, representing 23% of the total. The category of "aware" received 114 responses, making up 19% of the total. Lastly, the category of "partially aware" had 91 responses, constituting 16% of the total. These figures clearly demonstrate the varying levels of awareness, with some categories having higher levels of responses than others. This might be demonstrated more effectively by utilizing a pie chart.

Figure 1: Levels of Accessibility to Artificial Intelligence

Research Two: What is the perception of educators on the ease of use of artificial intelligence? Table 2 shows the frequency of usage of artificial intelligence.

		Perceived Ease of Use of Artificial Intelligence							
ITEMS		Very Difficult	Not Easy	to Easy	to Use	Very Easy	to Use		
		to us	Use	to	Use	Use	to	Frequency	%
		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	ChatGP T (Open.ai)	0	0	4	7.5	24	45.3	25	47.2
2	Diffit.ai	6	11.3	18	34.0	20	37.7	9	17.0
3	Magic School.a i	5	9.4	22	41.5	24	45.3	2	3.8
4	Bing.ai	5	9.4	12	22.6	18	34.0	18	34.0
5	Presenta tion.ai	5	9.4	17	32.1	16	30.2	15	28.3
6	Schemel y.app	5	9.4	13	24.5	26	49.1	9	17.0
7	Brisk teaching	4	7.5	18	34.0	19	35.8	12	22.6
8	Almana ck.ai	4	7.5	16	30.2	26	49.1	7	13.2
9	Lingotea ch.ai	6	11.3	16	30.2	24	45.3	7	13.2
10	Zozo solution s	5	9.4	19	35.8	19	35.8	10	18.9
11	Bard/Ge mini.ai	6	11.3	17	32.1	18	34.0	12	22.6
TOTAL		51		172		234		126	

Table 2 displays the perception of ease of use of artificial intelligence by educators across different applications or websites related to artificial intelligence. The category labeled "very difficult to

use" received 51 responses, accounting for 9% of the total. The category labeled "not easy to use" had 172 responses, representing 30% of the total. The category labeled "easy to use" received 234 responses, making up 40% of the total. Lastly, the category labeled "very easy to use" received 126 responses, accounting for 22% of the total. These figures indicate the different levels of artificial intelligence usage among educators with chatGPT being the highest on the easy to use response. A bar chart would provide a more lucid representation of this information.

Figure 2: Perceived Ease of Use of Artificial Intelligence

Research Three: What is the level of readiness of educators to adopt artificial intelligence in Ilorin, Kwara state?

Table 3 shows the readiness to adopt artificial intelligence by educators.

Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence										
ITEMS	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Agree		Strongly Agree			
	Frequen cy	%	Frequ ency	%	Frequ ency	%	Frequ ency	%		
1 It is important for Educators to use AI for planning their lessons.	1	1.9	0	0	15	28.3	37	69.8		
2 AI has potentials to ease	0	0	1	1.9	12	22.6	40	75.5		

	educators' tasks.								
3	Educators should use AI for assessment.	0	0	2	3.8	21	39.6	30	56.6
4	I can use AI to prepare for my next lesson	0	0	1	1.9	18	34.0	34	64.2
5	Educators should continue to use AI for instructional purposes.	1	1.9	0	0	17	32.1	35	66.0
TOTAL RESPONSES		2(1%)		4(2%)		83(31%)		176(66%)	

Table 3 shows how ready educators are to use various artificial intelligence tools and websites. The category denoted "Strongly Disagree" obtained 2 replies, indicating 1% of the overall total. The category labelled "disagree" received 4 comments, accounting for 2% of the overall total. The "agree" category attracted 83 responses, or about 31% of the total. Finally, the category marked "strongly agree" obtained 176 replies, representing 66% of the overall total. These statistics illustrate that educators are ready to use artificial intelligence. A pie chart would offer a more straightforward and concise depiction of this information.

Figure 3: Readiness to adopt Artificial intelligence

Hypothesis One: Accessibility does not significantly influence educators' readiness to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery in Ilorin, Kwara State

Table 4: This table shows the Pearson Correlation Coefficient between Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence and level of accessibility to Artificial Intelligence.

		Accessibility to Artificial Intelligence	to Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence
Accessibility to Artificial Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	-.160
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.253
	N	53	53
Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	-.160	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.253	
	N	53	53

p-value >0.05

Table 4 shows the association analysis conducted between Accessibility to Artificial Intelligence and Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence gave a Pearson correlation coefficient of -0.160. This coefficient shows a mild negative linear relationship between the two variables. However, the related significance value (Sig.) of 0.253 suggests that this association is not statistically significant at the typical 95% confidence level. This indicates that the correlation is very weak and negative, proving there's absolutely no linear relationship between educators' level of accessibility to artificial intelligence and Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence.

Hypothesis Two: Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence does not significantly influence educators' perceived ease of use of artificial intelligence in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Table 5: This table shows the Pearson Correlation Coefficient between Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence and perceived ease of use of Artificial Intelligence.

		Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence	Perceived Ease of Use of Artificial Intelligence
Readiness to Adopt Artificial Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	-.056
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.690
	N	53	53
Perceived Ease of Use of Artificial Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	-.056	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.690	
	N	53	53

p-value >0.05

Table 4 indicates the association between readiness to adopt and ease of use of artificial intelligence is determined to be at -0.056. This coefficient shows a very weak negative linear relationship between the two variables. However, the related significance level (Sig.) of 0.690 suggests that this association is not statistically significant at the standard significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, based on the presented data, the null hypothesis was accepted that there is no substantial association between readiness to adopt and the perceived ease of use of artificial intelligence.

Discussions

The respondents indicated their level of accessibility to artificial intelligence, indicating Chat GPT (Open.ai) as the most accessible for planning and preparing instructions followed by Bing.ai,

Presentation.ai, Schemely.app, Bard/Gemini.ai, Magic school, Zozo solutions, and Brisk teaching in descending order. There was low awareness of Almanack.ai, and Diffit.ai as indicated by the respondents. The AI tools and applications that the respondents referred to as accessible were perceived as easy to use except for Magic school. Almanack.ai, and Diffit.ai were perceived difficult to use with response a little above average. The respondents also indicated that they were ready to adopt artificial intelligence. The results indicated that educators' accessibility level does not influence perceived ease of use of artificial intelligence. Conclusions and future directions of the study on perceived ease of use give vital insights into educators' readiness to adopt AI in classrooms. By addressing these problems via user-centered design, solid support structures, and a clear emphasis on educational advantages, the road for a more integrated and successful use of AI for instructional delivery in schools is paved. Further study is required to evaluate the long-term influence of AI on learning outcomes and teacher burden. Therefore, it would be beneficial to research the effect of variables such as school resources, access to technology, and teacher demographics on AI adoption. Hence, addressing these characteristics will be critical for harnessing the potential of artificial intelligence to enhance educational experiences for all.

Conclusions

1. Educators' level of accessibility to artificial intelligence is above average and vary with different AI tools.
2. Educators' vary in their perception ease of use of artificial intelligence depending on the type of AI tools.
3. Educators are willing and ready to adopt artificial intelligence for instructional delivery in schools.
4. Accessibility does not significantly influence educators' readiness to adopt artificial intelligence.
5. Readiness to adopt does not significantly influence educators' perceived ease of use of artificial intelligence.

Recommendations

1. One way of overcoming the challenges of awareness is to train and retrain educators.
2. Enlighten educators on the use numerous artificial intelligence tools.
3. Educators should be encouraged by improving accessibility to artificial intelligence tools through stable and sustainable internet access.
4. Policies on sustainable use of AI and other emerging technologies should be made by education policy makers

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